
BUILDING THE WRITING HABIT: COLLABORATIVE WRITING

Mammadova Minavvar Firudin

*Ph. doctor, associate professor,
Military Institute named after Haydar Aliyev*

Aliyeva Sevda Murtuz

Ph. doctor, associate professor

Asadova Rumella Talib

Ph. doctor, senior teacher

National Aviation Academy, "Professional English Language"

***"Begin at the beginning" the King said, very gravely,
"and go on till you come to the end; then stop".***

from 'Alice's Adventures in Wonderland' by Lewis Carroll

Abstract

English writing has changed considerably over the centuries. Early fourteenth-century writing, for example, has significantly different spellings from present-day English and some letters were formed differently: a modern version of written communication, however, received via a mobile phone, can look like this message. Clearly writing has come a long way – or, has it?

How to teach writing begins by looking at the process that a competent speaker of English goes through after they decide to write a piece of text, and at how our understanding of this has implications for the way we should approach the teaching of writing. In this article we tried to show the ways of writing activities, (including handwriting, spelling, and punctuation) before going on to show examples of activities designed to help students write coherently in sentences and paragraphs.

Keywords: students creativity, unwillingness, writing activities, levels of challenge

Although some students are always happy to have a go at writing in English, others can be less keen. This unwillingness may derive from anxieties they have about their handwriting, their spelling, or their ability to construct sentences and paragraphs. And if these insecurities are reinforced because they are unable to complete writing tasks successfully, then the student's attitude to writing is likely to become more and more negative.

The students' reluctance to write can also be because they rarely write even in their own language, and so the activity feels alien. Another powerful disincentive is the fear that they have 'nothing to say' - a common response of many students when asked to write.[1] Finally, writing just does not interest some students: such people seem to be unwilling to invest the time and effort that they think a writing task demands.

With students like this who lack familiarity or confidence with writing (or indeed enthusiasm for it) we need to spend some time building the writing habit- that is making students feel comfortable as writers in English and so gaining their willing participation in more creative or extended activities. This will involve choosing the right kinds of activity-with appropriate levels of challenge- and providing them with enough language and information to allow them to complete writing tasks successfully.

Choosing writing tasks and activities

It is important that we choose writing activities which have a chance of appealing to our students – and which have, if possible, some relevance for them. Writing fairy stories might appeal to children but could fail to inspire a group of university students.

If we are lucky we will have a good idea of not only what kind of writing students are likely to have to

do in English in the future? But also what kind of subjects and tasks they will enjoy- or have enjoyed in the past. This will help us choose writing tasks either because students need them or because they are likely to be motivated by them because the tasks are engaging in themselves.

An engaging writing task is one of that involves students not just intellectually but emotionally as well: it amuses them, intrigues them, or makes them feel good.[2]

What engages people may be different for different students, but clearly the stimulus we provide will make a difference. Music for example, can be used to awaken the students creativity, especially if they respond particularly well to auditory input. Having students write jointly on the board or swap papers around caters for those who respond to kinesthetic stimulation (movement and physical activity). [3] Writing task can be initiated and conducted in a number of different ways, in other words, and if we are to build the writing habit in the greatest number of our students we need to be aware of the variety of tastes and interests they have.

Except in the most goal-focused ESP classes, students are likely to respond best to a wide variety of tasks, topics, and genres over a period of time.[4] Though we may want to revisit a writing genre- so that students can apply what they learned first time around for this second try – we will want to give students the widest range possible. Variety is as important in writing tasks and the activities that go with them as it is for other areas of language learning such as speaking, listening, and reading.

What students need?

As we saw at the beginning of this article, there are many reasons why students may not be confident or willing writers. In order to counteract these potential

problems we have to identify what our students need if they are to have a reasonable chance of success:

Information and task information- learners need to have the necessary information to complete the task. This means that they need to understand clearly what we want them to do and they need also, to be absolutely clear about any of the topic detail that we give them. If we ask them to respond to an invitation, for example, they need to have understood the details of the invitation, who they are writing to, and what is they are trying to achieve. If they are involved in a collaborative writing activity they need to know what they are writing about, who writes what, and how they writing sequence is going to progress.

Language- if students need specific language to complete a writing task we need to give it to them (or help them to find it). This may involve offering them phrases, parts of sentences, or words.[5]

Of course there are times when we just get students to write without thinking, to provoke their use of all and any of the language they know. But where a task depends on certain written formulate it would be pointless not to offer these to the students.

Ideas- teachers need to be able to suggest ideas to help students when they get stuck. For some this may be just a word or two. For others we may need to dictate a half sentence or even something more substantial. One of the skills of a good writing teachers is to be able to throw out suggestions without crowding out the individual students with too much oppressive detail. In order to do this we have to be aware of which students need more or less help and stimulation, especially where students are working on their own rather than collaboratively.

When students are involved in the kind of process writing or genre-based construction we talked about in the first two chapters of this book, the identification of suitable topics and tasks and an analysis of what they need to complete the tasks successfully are both absolutely vital. They are important, too, for tasks which aim to build the writing fluently and enthusiastically, often with more spontaneity and less actual preparation than in process and genre approaches. Two such areas of habit building are instant writing and collaborative writing.

Instant writing

There are stages in any lesson where students can be asked to write on the spot, without much in the way of preparation or warning: this is instant writing.

Because instant writing is not part of a long writing process, it can be used whenever the teacher feels it is appropriate. The tasks may each take only ten or fifteen minutes or be even shorter; but a regular diet of such tasks will boost students confidence, if they are appropriate, since each time they will have something worthwhile and interesting to show for their efforts.

The following activities provide some examples of instant writing.

Sentence writing

As we have seen, students can be asked to write sentences either as language reinforcement or in preparation for a forthcoming activity. The following activi-

ties could also be used for such purposes, but their purpose here is to make reluctant writers feel more comfortable and to remove the problems of those who think they have nothing to say:

Dictating sentences for completion – a very simply way of getting students to write creatively is to dictate part of a sentence which they then have to complete about themselves. For example, we can dictate the following:

“My favorite time of day is...”[6]

And students have to write the morning, or the evening, etc. This can be extended of course. The teacher can say: “Now write one sentence saying why you have chosen your time of day”.

Just about any incomplete sentence can be used in this way,as the following examples demonstrate:

“The one thing I should most like to learn is how to...”

“The best film I have ever seen is ...”

“One of the most exciting things that has ever happened to me is...”

Teacher can also dictate sentence frames. *If the topic is “animals “ we can say;*

“Although I like .../ I am not very keen on/ [7]

Writing sentences – students can be asked to write two or three sentences about a certain topic. For example, suppose students have been working on the topic of “hopes and ambitions”, they can write three sentences about how they would like their lives to change in the future. If they are discussing education, they can write sentences about why exams are a good thing or a bad thing. If they have been discussing anti-social behavior, the teacher can ask them to write three don’t sentences (e.g. Do not listen to loud music after eleven o’clock).

The weather forecast- at the beginning of the day the teacher asks students to write about themselves and their day as if they were writing a weather forecast; “What is the weather like now? Are you happy or tired, listless or energetic? How are you likely to feel later on? In the afternoon? ”

Activities like this work extremely well for some students, because they allow them to be creative in an amusing and thought-provoking way. Sentence writing is one way of getting students to write quickly while at the same time allowing them to write things that mean something to them personally.

Although we will deal with responses to student writing in detail in article, we should make some comments here about what teachers can do with the results of “habit—building” writing.

We have stressed that one of the purposes for the writing activities we have been looking at in this article is to give students engaging writing tasks that will help them become fluent writers. We have mentioned that benefit that successful production has for students confidence as writers.

In this article we have discussed:

-shown how by choosing the right tasks students will be keen to write

-talked about the need to help students to have “something to say” by giving appropriate task information , necessary language, and ,on occasions, patterns and schemes to follow.

-said that teachers need to give positive acknowledgement as well as more formal language feedback.

-looked at ways in which we can get students to write to each other whether by passing notes, by e-mail, in live chat, or by writing simulated letters.

References

1. Levine, A. and Reves. T. Does the Method of Vocabulary Presentation Make a difference? Canada: TESOL Journal, 8, 1990, 51 p.

2. Lieberman A. and Miller L. Their world and their work. New York: Teachers College Press, 1992, 104 p.

3. Little D. Learner Autonomy. Definitions, Issues, and Problems. Dublin: Authentic Language

Learning Resources Limited, 1991, 262 p.

4. Littlejohn D. Autonomy in Language Learning. Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press, 1996, 210 p.

5. Littlewood W. Communicative Language Teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1981, 207 p.

6. Louis de B. Captain Corellis' mandolin. UK: Vintage, 1995, 436 p.

7. Minavvar F. Mammadova "linguo-didactic basics of the english-language training in higher military educational institutions" 2025-Baku, 306 p. (manuscript copyright)